

THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN PREVENTING NEGLECT AND JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

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Abstract: This article examines the concept and main areas of activity of internal affairs bodies in preventing neglect and delinquency among minors.

Keywords: minor, internal affairs bodies, administrative activity, prevention, delinquency, cooperation, legislation.

In our country, large-scale efforts are underway to create a comprehensive legal system aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of minors, as well as promoting their physical, intellectual, spiritual and moral development. Although, according to statistics [1], the analysis of the number of identified minors by the end of 2024 showed a decrease of 235 individuals compared to the same period in 2023, this should not lead to complacency, as «we have set ourselves the task of raising our work to a new level in fostering a harmoniously developed, physically healthy, and spiritually mature young generation» [2].

The internal affairs bodies (IAB) of the Republic of Uzbekistan play a key role in preventing juvenile neglect and delinquency. Their activities are aimed at ensuring public safety, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of children, and creating conditions for their full development.

In accordance with the law [3], the internal affairs bodies (IAB) are among the key entities in the system for preventing juvenile neglect and delinquency. The specialized units of the OVD responsible for this work are the divisions for the prevention of juvenile offenses and the centers for social and legal assistance to minors. Other OVD units also participate and provide necessary support within the scope of their authority.

The main areas of activity of the internal affairs bodies (IAB) in this field, in accordance with the legislation [4], include:

Firstly, the identification and prevention of juvenile neglect and offenses. The internal affairs bodies (IAB) conduct operations to identify unsupervised children on the streets, at railway stations, in basements, and other places where they may gather; they refer homeless children to rehabilitation centers; and they work to locate their parents or guardians and hold them accountable for inadequate upbringing, among other measures. In 2024, 25,331 minors were interviewed, 267 were referred for compulsory treatment, and 14,648 were removed from preventive monitoring lists [5]. In addition, the OVD are involved in identifying and preventing crimes and administrative offenses committed by minors, the involvement of children and adolescents in criminal activities by adults, and the illegal exploitation of child labor, including begging and prostitution.

Secondly, the implementation of individualized preventive work. According to the law [6], individualized preventive measures are carried out in relation to minors who: are unsupervised or homeless; have committed antisocial acts; are held in specialized educational

institutions or centers for social and legal assistance; do not attend or systematically skip classes in educational institutions without valid reasons; have committed administrative offenses; have been exempted from criminal liability on the basis of an act of amnesty or due to the insignificance of the act or the person's diminished social danger, or due to the offender's sincere repentance or reconciliation with the victim, or in cases where it is determined that the minor can be corrected without punishment; have committed socially dangerous acts but are under the age of criminal responsibility, or due to significant developmental delays not related to mental disorders, are unable to fully understand the nature of their actions; are accused of committing crimes and are under non-custodial preventive measures; have been exempted from criminal punishment through the application of compulsory measures; have been conditionally released early from serving their sentence; have been exempted from punishment due to loss of social danger or sincere repentance, or by an act of amnesty or pardon; have received a deferred sentence; are conditionally sentenced or sentenced to correctional labor or other non-custodial penalties; have been released from penal institutions or returned from specialized educational institutions; are registered in healthcare institutions due to mental disorders and are prone to committing offenses; as well as in relation to families found to be in a socially dangerous situation.

Thus, the internal affairs bodies (IAB) maintain records and work with minors who are under preventive supervision or are considered at risk. As part of this work, officers of the preventive units: conduct preventive conversations with minors and their parents (guardians); monitor their adherence to educational and leisure routines; and carry out regular inspections of families where children's rights may be violated (such as cases of violence, lack of proper supervision, or a criminogenic environment). Currently, the electronic system «E-Voyaga Yetmagan», which allows for the registration of unsupervised minors, has been fully implemented at the national level.

Thirdly, working with disadvantaged families. Officers of the IAB cooperate with social protection and education authorities, conducting raids and inspections of families where violations of minors' rights may occur. Based on the findings, OVD officers may: issue a warning to parents; hold parents administratively accountable (such as imposing fines or mandatory work); prepare materials for submission to court regarding the deprivation of parental rights.

In order to prevent juvenile neglect, in 2024, 104,139 children who were unsupervised in public places were identified. Of these, 1,715 children were placed in social and legal assistance centers, 34 children were placed in educational and correctional institutions, and 789 children without parental care were assigned guardians and custodians. Additionally, 778 parents who had a negative influence on their children's upbringing were employed, and 6,828 children were engaged in elective clubs [7]. In addition, on April 5, 2025, working groups consisting of specialists from the Department of Crime Prevention of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, in collaboration with the Embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Russian Federation, returned 16 minors without parental care to the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of these, 15 children were placed in the Social and Legal Assistance Center for Minors of the Tashkent City Internal Affairs Directorate, and 1 was placed in the state enterprise «Children's Home of Tashkent». These children received medical, psychological, and social assistance [8].

Fourthly, cooperation with bodies and institutions that carry out the prevention of juvenile neglect and delinquency, including: child welfare commissions; educational management bodies and educational institutions; guardianship and custody authorities; health management bodies and healthcare institutions; labor and social protection authorities; NGOs and international organizations and others. The IAB actively cooperate with educational institutions by: conducting preventive conversations with students about the consequences of offenses; monitoring discipline in schools; responding to reports of violence and bullying among students. Thus, in 2024, in Uzbekistan, 5,920 minors were returned to school, 8,136 were engaged in sports activities, 1,416 were involved in small business activities, and 2,719 were placed in «Barkamol Avlod» centers [9].

Fifthly, rehabilitation and resocialization of offenders. For minors who have committed offenses but have not reached the age of criminal responsibility, corrective measures are applied: referral to specialized educational and correctional institutions; inclusion in social adaptation and psychological support programs; assistance with employment for minors released from places of detention.

Despite successful initiatives, there are issues in the organization of the IAB's work. For example, there is a low level of cooperation with educational institutions, a shortage of specialized staff, insufficient preventive work with the families of minors, and other challenges.

All of this requires addressing the problems and shortcomings arising in the administrative activities of the IAB in preventing juvenile neglect and delinquency, as well as developing recommendations aimed at further enriching its scientific and theoretical foundations.

Based on the views outlined above, it can be stated that the issues of improving the effectiveness of the administrative activities of the internal affairs bodies (IAB) in preventing juvenile neglect and delinquency are directly related to the legal, organizational-tactical, material-technical, and personnel foundations of the field under analysis. In our opinion, addressing the problems and shortcomings arising in these four areas will have a positive impact on enhancing the effectiveness of these activities.

Thus, the administrative activities of the internal affairs bodies (IAB) in preventing juvenile neglect and delinquency in Uzbekistan are based on a comprehensive approach that includes legislative measures, individualized work with minors and their families, as well as cooperation with other governmental and public institutions. Continuous improvement of these activities and consideration of modern challenges are key to effective prevention and ensuring the well-being of the younger generation

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